

RESEARCH OF NATIONAL CULTURE AND ART HISTORY ON THE EVE OF INDEPENDENCE (CINEMA AND THEATER FOR EXAMPLE)

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Abstract: In this article, the study of the history of culture and the independent study of the history of culture and art, and the material and technical base of the national cinema, theater, and art through them to see the past, history, and Uzbek the peculiarities of the revival and development of the creativity of the people are highlighted.

Key words: Culture, art, cinema, theater, decision, decree, document, reform.

During the period of colonialism and autocracy, our culture suffered a lot. Especially the followers of the communist ideology tried to destroy the culture of our people. Despite great losses, the Uzbek people managed to preserve their identity and national culture. It is never possible to completely destroy this national culture from the social consciousness of a people with a high spiritual culture and strong roots. So there was an opportunity to restore the cultural heritage and raise it to a higher level¹.

During the years of independence, science, culture, and art developed at an unprecedented level in Uzbekistan. As a result of the purification of these phenomena from false elements such as partisanship, classism, ideology, their role and social importance in the development of society and nation has increased significantly. In particular, it should be noted that the attention to the science of history has increased.

"A nation that forgets history and does not learn the right lessons from it will always go astray," said the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov. - That is the meaning of the saying that there is no future without historical memory. From this point of view, I think that people, especially young people, should remember the events that happened in our recent past. There are a number of reasons why the issue is being addressed in this context. First, during the former autocratic regime, the history of the Uzbek people and statehood was grossly distorted. It is said that the Uzbek people were illiterate and uncivilized until the October coup d'état.

¹ Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an invincible force. — T.: Ma'naviyat, 2008. P.141

Secondly, all the works written on our national history were labeled as "attempt at nationalism". The authors of such works were subjected to political repressions. they were tired.

Only when the essence of national independence is understood, the feeling of true patriotism will be awakened in people, not only the cultural heritage of the past. rather, there is a feeling of deeper understanding of the issues of the modern and, moreover, the future culture and spirituality of the people. National independence has such a powerful force that the struggle for the destiny, culture and national values of one's nation, people and people has become a human belief of every citizen. In turn, the development of national culture helped every person to join the flow of modern development. Since the first days of independence, a number of music competitions have been held. In particular, in 1992, the national competition of tanbur, sato, koshnai, trumpet and other national music performers called "Equals of the Ages" was held in Tashkent, and in April, the competition of amateur puppet theater teams in Tashkent region. , as well as auditions called "Eternal Voices" of performers of the works of famous artists Jorakhan Sultanov, Saidjon Kalonov, Komiljon Jabbarov, Nabijon Hasanov, Komiljon Otaniyozov, Fakhriddin Sadikov, Janak Shomuratov were held. In the same year, the 9th traditional competition of folklore groups, askiya, amateurs and clowns held in Kok, and the 11th traditional competition of lapar and yalla performers held in Tashkent are important for the development of our national art. contributed.

Due to the independence, a new system of culture began to emerge in our Republic. In particular, the Council of the Republic "Spirituality and Enlightenment", "Education Center", "Uzbekkino", "Uzbeknavo", "Uzbekraqs", "Uzbekmuzey", "Uzbekteatr" , the establishment of many cultural and educational organizations, such as the Academy of Arts, National Cultural Centers, became the basis for the development of the main areas of the republic's spirituality.

During the years of independence, the contests "New Generation", "Voice of the Future", "The Motherland is One", "The Motherland is One", "New Names" and other competitions have their own direction, specific purpose and have duties.

The whole world recognizes that great historical works have been carried out in the development of national culture in our country. We can safely say that a new solid foundation of the culture of independent Uzbekistan has been created².

² Karaboyev U., Soatov G'. Culture of Uzbekistan "Thinking - Boston" TASHKENT, 2011. P.168

Many newly created organizations in the state system, for example, "Uzbekteleradio" company, "Uzbekkino", "Uzbekistan Art Academy", "Uzbeknavo", "Uzbekteatr", "Uzbektourism" are effective. are operating.

In the following years, in order to develop our national culture and art, critical analysis, deep study of the content and essence of the works carried out in the years of independence, and on this basis, the reformation and improvement of the management system, in which the manifestation of culture and art in the political life of the society and It was considered as the main issue of the agenda that special attention should be paid to such important aspects as the rational use of the great role played by our people in the way of life. Accordingly, at the initiative of the head of our state, the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs was abolished, and in accordance with the Presidential Decree, the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State Committee for Physical Education and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan were established on its basis.

On August 16, 2017, the signing of the Presidential Decree "On the establishment of the Fergana regional branch of the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan" was of special importance in the history of culture and art of our country.

On October 16, 2017, "On the establishment of the Culture and Art Development Fund under the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan", on October 18, 2017, "On strengthening the material and technical base of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan On June 27, 2018, the Presidential Decree "On measures to organize the activities of the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan" was signed³.

Presidential decree "On bringing cinema art and industry to a new level, further improving the system of state support of the industry" signed on April 7, 2021 and "Improving the state management system in the field of cinematography and the representatives of the industry The Tashkent International Film Festival "Masterpiece of the Silk Road" held on the basis of the Decision "On creating suitable conditions for creative activity" was a reflection of the synthesis of Uzbek cinema with world cinema.

The work carried out in our country in the direction of the development of culture and art is extremely consistent with the priority measures aimed at ensuring spiritual

³ Haydarov A. Madaniyat - milliy yuksalish poydevori. - Toshkent: Oltin meros press, 2021. B.478

development and bringing the industry to a new level, reflected in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan. We can say that these reforms will contribute to the practical realization of the idea "From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development" based on the principle of goodness and humanity, and the realization of the concept of "New Uzbekistan - an enlightened society". Each nation occupies a strong place in world civilization with the power of its culture and art. The development of this sector is one of the important factors that show the strength and potential of the country, the value of the people, its reputation and status in the world⁴.

In short, since the first days of our independence, the restoration of the immense, priceless spiritual and cultural heritage created by our ancestors over many centuries has risen to the level of state policy. After gaining independence, the leadership of Uzbekistan, first of all, taking into account the needs and aspirations of our people, paid great attention to the restoration of ancient holidays and the formation of new independence holidays.

In the years of independence, the material and technical base of the national cinema and theater arts was strengthened, through which the past and history can be seen, remembered, sensed, studied, and therefore the process of revival and development of the Uzbek national creativity is accelerating. Also, the "History of Uzbekistan" TV channel was launched in order to make our youth aware of the history of our country.

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⁴ Nazarbekov O. Yuksak e'tibor va ehtirom bizga kuch, shijoat beradi // Xalq so'zi gazetasi. - Toshkent: 2022. - B.4